

Cover

RITMOCORE **RITMOCORE PPI - Arrhythmias monitoring** **and comprehensive care**

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<p>Abstract</p>	<p>RITMOCORE builds on the experience of the STOP&GO Project to address the evolution of the treatment of elderly patients who use or who are in need of a pacemaker (PM). The goal is to reduce in-hospital visits and to improve patients' quality of life through effective use of ICT and coordination of care processes.</p> <p>Despite the benefits reported in several studies, the European Society of Cardiology survey (2015) shows that remote monitoring (RM) was only available for 22% of PM patients. Reimbursement for RM is perceived (83%) as a major barrier to large-scale adoption, as are technical barriers and workload issues (13% each).</p> <p>To overcome this, RITMOCORE moves from purchasing devices to purchasing a service, in which the necessary ingredients to implement the new care scheme can be encapsulated and combined to complement the resources that not easily available into the care system. The main pillars of the service are: Remote Monitoring of pacemakers, Patients Activation; Coordinated Care and Risk Sharing models.</p> <p>RITMOCORE aims to i) contribute to awareness of public procurement to boost ICT innovation applied to active and healthy ageing; ii) contribute to an open and comprehensive socio-economic evidence base for ICT investments in the field that can support the development of sustainable business models; and iii) provide data to regulatory and legislative processes to inform policy measures that foster the take-up of ICT solutions.</p> <p>Prior Information Notice will be published shortly in the OJEU, and it will be followed by the information concerning an Open Market Consultation procedure.</p>

RITMOCORE

RITMOCORE PPI - Arrhythmias monitoring and comprehensive care

Marcel Olivé Elias and Esther Arévalo de Andrés,
Agency for Health Quality and Assessment of
Catalonia (AQuAS) (Spain)

RITMOCORE builds on the experience of the STOP&GO Project to address the evolution of the treatment of elderly patients who use or who are in need of a pacemaker (PM). The goal is to reduce in-hospital visits and to improve patients' quality of life through effective use of ICT and coordination of care processes.

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AT A GLANCE

Programme:	Horizon 2020
Duration:	01.11.2016 – 31.12.2020
Main outcome:	Reduction of in-hospital visits and Improvement of patients' quality of life through effective use of ICT and coordination of care processes.
Website:	www.ritmcore-ppi.eu

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COMPLETE

Cloud-MicroPhysics-Turbulence-Telemetry

Daniela Tordella, Politecnico di Torino (Italy)

Understanding cloud behaviour is fundamental to weather prediction and climate modelling, which justifies the need for more explorative observation. The COMPLETE project will contribute to closing the knowledge gap, allowing young researchers to develop their scientific competences specific to this research field as well as key professional skills applicable to both the academic and industrial environments.

Clouds represent the largest source of uncertainty in weather prediction and climate modelling. This is rooted in the fact that clouds depend on physical and chemical processes over a huge range of scales, from the nucleation of droplet at the nanoscale, to the collisions of micro-sized droplets, to airflow dynamics on the scale of thousands of metres.

The mathematical treatment of multi-scale phenomena is currently very difficult. Any improvement depends upon the availability of precise experimental data sets.

AT A GLANCE

Programme:	H2020-MSCA-ITN-2015 Marie Skłodowska Curie Action
Duration:	01.06.2016 – 31.05.2020
Main outcome:	To develop an inter-multidisciplinary training network to prepare high-potential researchers that will advance our understanding of cloud physics
Website:	www.complete-h2020network.eu

The research objective of COMPLETE is to establish connections between events occurring on various scales. Additionally, the project aims to develop an international and multidisciplinary training network that will prepare researchers with both scientific and industry-oriented skills in order to advance our understanding of these multi-scale complex natural phenomena. The training programme will combine the scientific investigation of specific aspects of cloud physics and related turbulent dynamics with training in key professional skills. This includes an exceptional experimental programme, including in-field and laboratory experiments, numerical simulations, the design and development of advanced fast temperature probes, velocity micro-electronic and mechanical devices, and innovative atmospheric mini green expandable radio-probes; all are aimed at the production of new datasets required to reduce the fragmentation of results and knowledge in this field.

